

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: FLOMO

FIRST NAME: MOGANA

PROGRAM CODE: DSDD

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER:1

INSTRUCTOR: GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: MSWord 2010 on Windows 8

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING RP1

1) INTRODUCTION

It has been a difficult time for me to begin a doctoral study at EUCLID due to my current engagements as an official of the government in my country. My decision to join EUCLID came as a result of the current job I do; because I need to improve my knowledge in development works to enable me properly impact my society. EUCLID is a unique university and can add up to what I have learned in other institutions. Reminding me of those fundamental skills I need to have to enhance my studies at this very beginning is a beautiful step forward. Technical writing is very important for those with the highest level of education as they are expected to produce papers of the best standards. As I have seen in the EUCLID program design, A clear understanding of this course will fuel my ability to complete my Ph.D. in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy as well as help me to become a stronger and credible researcher both in my current portfolio and other new portfolios I may come across soon.

2) PERIOD 1 COURSEPACK

This course, “International Academic Writing,” though it had up to 83 pages, does not have a table of contents, contains beneficial information required for any good doctoral program. It is appropriately organized into “Essay Writing: The basics” which looks at starting an essay, researching the topic, organizing the idea, which includes the writing of the plan, and writing the essay (EUCLID 2015, 2–4). This section also teaches how the referencing, editing and handling of an essay are done (EUCLID 2015, 5). Key is

this document carefully selected by EUCLID to strengthen the writing of a dissertation, are points like using the proper file saving format, consistency of spelling and punctuations, and remembering to run a spelling check as well as the appropriate use of comma (EUCLID 2015, 7). A successful Ph.D. would not be possible if the thesis fails to consider other writers who have contributed to the work. As such, the pack presents plagiarism, which is the illegal use of papers, journals, books, etc. to extract information for an academic work without proper referencing or citing those sources (EUCLID 2015, 8–42). I was attracted to the rules of thumb for writing papers. Amongst other things, the rules have reminded me to state the central thesis of my paper near or at the beginning, remain focused, avoid leading sweeping generalizations. Also, I learned that writing your paper is important and that I must avoid writing in a barring and clumsy manner (EUCLID 2015, 43–44). Writing is interesting when the writer learns to support his assertions (EUCLID 2015, 44) and take the views you are discussing as significant as possible (EUCLID 2015, 44).

I had gained so e interest in the “LIT-101 Review” as it was an excellent reminder for me about some of the things that are required or must be considered when writing a good Ph.D. paper. This section helped me refreshed me in remembering the little things we usually overlook when as it touched the use of possessives. As it is said, “Any possessive singular now takes “s’ even if the noun ends in “s” (EUCLID 2015, 47). The correct use of “its” and “it’s” as well as “your” and “you’re” (EUCLID 2015, 47) are clear, and every good writer would ensure their proper use.

3) THE WRITING STYLE

In the style guide, I learned the proper use of “which” and “that”. I have never learned what “restrictive” and “non-restrictive” phrases (EUCLID 2015, 48) are. EUCLID has now explained to me what these phrases are. From now onward, I will now know how the place these two words as long as I can identify phrases as “restrictive” or “non-restrictive” (EUCLID 2015, 48).

Observing the writing style makes your paper to be neat and well organized. The packet explained in detail, the types of style a writer must use. “In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing styles are consistent (EUCLID 2015, 52). Using consistent style shows the reader; the writer knows what he is doing, and that the writer knows the rules and adds more value to the work. I learned in this section that preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling, use of abbreviations, etcetera., were essential components of writing (EUCLID 2015, 52). Using a quotation mark, as I learned in school, helps a writer to say more about a topic, while using the words of another person. The correct use of quotations there become very important when writing an academic paper. Using our style guide facilitates the usage is British and the other American (EUCLID 2015, 59). Like quotations, all punctuations are very important and placing them the right way has also been addressed in our guide. The use of punctuation inside quotation marks is the American style. However, I have always used my punctuations outside the quotation mark, though I believed all those years that rite as an American does. Frankly, I have often confused the two styles, and the EUCLID

guide has brought me back to my senses, reminding me of being uninformed in my writings (EUCLID 2015, 59).

4) A TALE OF TWO STYLES

Several different styles could be used when writing a research or academic papers. However, at EUCLID, I see that the two styles will be used in our works. I think is a way of keeping the students focused at these styles and permitting them to become very used to these styles, which would eventually improve our writing skills and allow us writes papers that would represent the university. Generally, I see that a typical response paper is using the APA style, whereas major scholarly works are done using the Turabian, also called the Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2015, 66). The two styles, APA and Turabian, look great for the academic work at EUCLID. I am convinced that the Turabian Style is going to improve my writing and add new flavors to them.

As part of the Turabian styling, I have also learned how to use acronyms, especially at the beginning of sentences (EUCLID, 2015, 66). I have never known this rule and have made numerous mistakes in this regard. I now have the tool that will allow me to use acronyms only if there is no other way to put it at the beginning of a sentence (EUCLID 2015, 66).

This coursepack has also shown me how to format my papers before publishing them correctly. What I see here is that writing is not all to the game but putting it in the right perspectives to allow readers' taste for the paper is even more critical. The proper setting of the margins, fonts, and indenting are important things to observe when writing (EUCLID 2015, 71).

5) CONCLUSION

A Ph.D. is a great achievement. Therefore, EUCLID's approach to developing the writing skills of students doing a Ph.D. is a beautiful undertaking. I already have the feeling that my three years of study at EUCLID will make me into a different person in academia. It is always important to observe the styles, languages, and format of the academic papers we do write. Usually, in other graduate schools, it is believed that students have gained enough knowledge and skills required to do a master's or a Ph.D. program. The case of EUCLID is different. The institution tries to remind students of the fundamental things that students might have forgotten during all their years of study at various institutions.

Finally, the coursepack helped me to be able to use the right type of language settings to avoid confusing the US and the UK language styles when writing. The refresher in the use of the best grammar and the pieces of counsel to write in a manner and form that would present my work to be great is appreciated and rewarding.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.